

ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS OF AGROFORESTRY IN LITHUANIA – PROJECTIONS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract. In Lithuania, the potential of agroforestry has been largely unexplored from either an environmental or economic perspective. There are no clearly established local methodological elements that would allow assessing the potential scope of new activities in Lithuania. The results of the article show that it makes sense to develop agroforestry activities in a significant part of the land area, but this activity is more relevant for large farms. This is especially relevant in those regions that do not have particularly fertile land areas and opportunities for diversification of activities. The forecast activity volumes are assessed based on good foreign experience - this is how the volume of sustainable agroforestry activities in the relevant land area is determined. Foreign models are adapted to the Lithuanian case - it is considered that there is still a lot of land use in Lithuania, farms are still in the formation stage, and the enlargement of areas can significantly affect the volume of agroforestry in the long term. Consolidation in agriculture will continue in the coming decades, and the enlargement of areas can open new prospects for agroforestry.

Keywords: *agroforestry, diversification, alternative agricultural practice, Lithuania.*

Introduction

The agricultural-forestry (agroforestry) sector in Lithuania does not have sustainable traditions. Business entities and individuals have favorable conditions for engaging in traditional forestry, based on consolidation of areas. The average forest holding in Lithuania in 2020 reached 3.4 ha; organic development through acquisitions is relevant for existing forestry entities, not the breeding of green spaces on agricultural land. In Lithuania, there are fragmented efforts to develop energy green spaces, but there is no unified political direction on how to ensure biomass supply and how to expand the volume of energy green spaces. In this situation, it is more relevant for Lithuania to use the concept of agroforestry common in the European Union. According to relevant EU documents, agroforestry is considered the integration of trees, shrubs and agricultural plants on the same land area. This can be done through membranous plant belts on agricultural land, short-rotation plantation cultivation. The biomass rotation period is 3-5 years.

Agroforestry is not legally regulated. Lithuania has amateur examples where energy crops are grown in small quantities - willow, poplar. However, a certain volume of energy wood exploitation can be obtained by analyzing the conversion of abandoned land areas. The amount of abandoned land has decreased by 45,000 ha since 2015. (Agricultural Data Center, 2025). A large part of these areas was overgrown with honey bushes, which were later processed into

biomass for the energy needs. In addition, in the 2020s, the cultivation of energy crops on agricultural land was encouraged. This method of cultivation was clearly limited due to the risk of damaging general land reclamation systems. The imbalance between agricultural and forestry activities allowed to see an unfilled activity environment, which is summarized by the principle of agricultural-forestry activities. Mixed farming practices used worldwide have not taken hold in Lithuania due to farmers' disposal of forest land and the constant absorption of abandoned land - this has allowed some farmers to create a parallel cash flow from additional activities.

Currently, there are two types of activity closest to the agroforestry direction – growing energy crops (willow, poplar) and maintaining landscape elements. In parallel, new forest areas are being declared (category “Forest breeding”), but this is considered a forestry initiative. With the emergence of the possibility of declaring groups of trees and shrubs as landscape elements, a clear growth of alternative farming activities is visible. After excluding forest breeding areas, the remaining areas can be considered a certain basis for the development of agroforestry, since the farmers declaring these areas have competence in the development and maintenance of energy crop areas. Part of the future forest breeding areas can be used for agroforestry activities, more specifically – for the cultivation of wood and livestock (Mercer, Li, Stainback, Alavalapati 2017). This synergy would allow the creation of biotopes of high environmental value, based on natural development processes. Currently, incentive measures for melliferous plant belts have been legalized. However, it is necessary to provide clear opportunities for exploiting these strips, generating income from forestry activities, while ensuring their reforestation. By establishing clear legal regulations and incentive mechanisms, positive developments in the development of agriculture-forestry (agroforestry) can be expected. The aim of the article - to determine the economic logic of agroforestry for the Lithuanian case.

Literature review

Currently, incentives for melliferous plant belts are legalized. However, it is necessary to provide clear opportunities for the exploitation of these belts, receiving income from forestry activities, while ensuring their regrowth. By establishing clear legal regulation and incentive mechanisms, positive developments in the development of agroforestry (agroforestry) can be expected. Currently, the main advantages and disadvantages of this farming method can be distinguished:

Advantages of agroforestry:

Economic value:

- Cost optimization through reduced tillage. By choosing the alternative of planting the entire available land area with energy crops, annual tillage is avoided, and the entire area is eventually covered with growing energy crops (Kay et al, 2019). At the end of the growing period, the plants are cut and, depending on legal regulations and the farmer's decisions, they can be allowed to re-sprout. The farmer avoids the costs of annual tillage, fertilization, spraying, and other annual agricultural operations during the entire maturation period of energy crops.
- Elimination of the influence of weather conditions (more stable income). The development of agriculture and forestry allows to substantially reduce the influence of unstable weather on future income (Cai, Aguilar, 2021). Energy crops are perennial; therefore, their growth process occurs regardless of daily changes in weather conditions. Harvesting is determined by agronomic conditions and can be carried out essentially regardless of the weather conditions prevailing on the day of harvest.

Environmental value:

- Less soil erosion (due to less frequent tillage). When developing agroforestry activities, tillage is minimized, associated only with the insertion of seedlings into the ground. Tillage can be postponed for 10-15 years depending on the possibility of regrowth of previously planted seedlings and the avoidance of negative impacts on land reclamation systems (Nair, 2011). The. During the entire growth period of energy crops, the conditions for soil erosion disappear, and natural, local ecosystems based on vegetation and low-lying fauna are formed.

- CO₂ absorption. Energy crops have relevant CO₂ storage and fixation properties. There are clear periods when CO₂ is accumulated and released back into the atmosphere. As an energy crop grows, CO₂ is constantly accumulated inside the plant. CO₂ is released from the energy crop when it is burned (Sobola, Amadi, Jamala, 2015). Meanwhile, this gas can remain in the soil for a longer period if a decision is made to allow existing crops to regrow. This creates the opportunity to harvest a new crop at the end of the rotation period, and CO₂ is fixed in the depths of the soil. In the case of land adaptation for crops or livestock farming, the soil is tilled with a surface mill, 20 cm. deep. It allows to avoid plowing, which is particularly harmful to the soil.
- Better use of abandoned lands for CO₂ absorption. Abandoned, uncultivated land areas can be particularly suitable for agroforestry. Without destroying the formed soil structure, conditions arise for the exploitation of energy crops and other activities, such as animal husbandry (Moreno et al, 2018). A significant obstacle to agricultural and forestry activities on abandoned lands is the waterlogging of areas. In other cases, there are no obstacles to using abandoned areas for energy purposes.

Social value:

- Promoting short biomass supply chains. Local biomass produced by farmers can be used to heat local facilities, such as regional schools, public or private buildings. This would reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transporting biomass to the facilities that use them (van Noordwijk, 2021). Short supply chains would open up avenues for smaller energy crop producers to enter the market and develop agroforestry activities, as they would not have to invest in excess transportation capacity.

Disadvantages:

Economic disadvantages:

- Limitations of agroforestry in Lithuania. A fundamental obstacle to the development of agroforestry in Lithuania is the largely unregulated concept and the ability to combine different farming methods on one piece of land. The lack of legal clarity and the absence of incentive measures limit farmers' opportunities to engage in this activity. Currently, legal acts or relevant decrees do not provide for a maximum period for growing such plants or solutions for declaring crops. In the Lithuanian General Plan "Lithuania 2030", priority agroforestry regions are identified in the column "Bioproductive farm activities and incentive measures". Based on this document, it is necessary to determine further factors for promoting agroforestry.
- Large land area requirement to ensure stable income. One of the main obstacles to the development of agroforestry is the large land area requirement to ensure economic viability. Due to the specifics of energy crop cultivation, the first income from the grown production may come after at least 5 years. Until then, income from production is not received, and the structure of direct payments for these crops is currently not sustainable and provides certainty for farms (Stancheva, Bencheva, Petkova, Piralkov, 2007). To orient farms towards agroforestry, a clear compensation mechanism for soil protection without cultivating it is necessary. At the same time, the significance of the effect of economies of scale is particularly pronounced here - it will be easier for those farms that manage more arable land to reorient agricultural activities.

Appropriate legal regulation of agroforestry and creation of incentive measures can help develop this sector, which is important for ensuring Lithuania's energy independence. It is necessary to emphasize that this branch of the economy is most suitable for farms managing large areas of land, as they can create a sustainable process of transition to agroforestry with minimal loss of income. In the case of small farms, state support would most likely not offset the positive impact on the soil and environment, since the economic viability of farms must be increased primarily through income from production sales, and not through subsidies.

Methodology

In the case of economic viability assessment, the focus is on the formed thesis that agroforestry makes the most sense for larger farms, which can form an optimal green area in the long term, capable of forming a stable cash flow. The additional income stream will come in approximately 5-10 years. The elements of economic viability projections are related to information from the last three years. A sensitivity analysis is also performed to assess possible changes in the price of production. The profitability evaluation is carried out based on

the principle of conservatism, assuming that some of the plants grown on agricultural areas based on agroforestry will be left for a longer period for sustainability purposes. It is appreciated that not all of the area allocated for agroforestry will be exploited at one time. This will allow the development of already formed ecosystems. Economic viability studies are carried out based on a typical example:

- A 5-ha land area suitable for grain farming is used for the assessment,
- The field is reclaimed, not waterlogged, the soil is typical and found in a large part of Lithuania,
- Out of 5 ha. 1 ha will be allocated for agroforestry activities.

According to the developed characteristics of the article, the possibilities of extracting wood production from agricultural land are assessed. In this case, the main dominant wood species are used (Table 1). Coniferous wood, which is characterized by low short-term growth productivity, is not included in the calculations. The cultivation of Christmas trees, which is prevalent on some farms, cannot be attributed to agroforestry activities due to the lack of opportunities to combine this activity with the cultivation of agricultural land. Instead, the article proposes new branches of activity that would increase the economic viability of farms, especially small ones. Typical plants with high economic value and favorable exploitation opportunities have been selected. These plants are assessed according to their economic properties - the ratio of growth rate and profitability. In addition, the possibility of processing these trees in Lithuanian wood industry enterprises is assessed.

Table 1

Characteristics of annual wood volume growth in different year groups

Wood type	Year of growth	Stand volume growth m ³ /ha
Birch	10	4,5
Alder	10	4,1
Aspen	10	3,9
Willow	5	4,6
Ash	10	4,3

Source: based on Abalikštienė, Kuliešis, Tebėra, 2013

The table provides information on willow growth for a 5-year period. Since willow is a short-rotation plant, it takes less time for it to reach optimal production than plants that dominate forests. Willow is suitable for agroforestry if it is grown in accordance with established practices in the world. In addition, the excessive growth of willow poses a threat to state-owned land reclamation systems. The use of willow is limited exclusively to energy needs - wood chips are produced from willow, which is a product traded on the biomass exchange.

Results

First, the potential economic benefits created by agroforestry are assessed, the wood areas grown on agricultural land are sold as biomass for energy (Table 2). The analysis presented indicates all types of production presented with calculations of their energy value. According to the calculations presented, the income received from growing trees on agricultural land is relatively low in the case where there is no appropriate scale of such activity. Until solutions for promoting such activities through direct payments are created, it is likely that the smallest farms will continue traditional agricultural activities, which provide annual income. The creation of incentive solutions would allow farmers to receive direct payments from the cultivation of temporary plantations, thus reducing the need to work the land in a traditional way. The currently existing payment for the maintenance and care of landscape elements does not create conditions for their exploitation for economic purposes. This type of direct payment could be considered an environmental bonus for the decision of farmers to allocate a certain area of land for extensive agroforestry activities.

Table 2

Projected revenue from the sale of biomass for energy (after 10 years)

Fuel type	Total gain m ³ /ha	Total gain sq. m ² /ha	Energy value, MWh	Biomass price, EUR/MWh*	Revenue generated, EUR
Birch	45	40	36	25	900
Alder	41	35	29		725
Aspen	39	30	21		525
Willow	23	18	13		325
Ash	43	40	40		1000

* The biomass price is set based on the average price in the Lithuanian zone of the Baltpool exchange for 2021-2025.

Source: based on Abalikštienė, Kuliešis, Tebėra, 2023; Baltpool, 2025a

In some agricultural-forestry areas, production can also be sold as a higher value-added product. This is related to the decision made on which type of wood to grow. Table 3 shows that in the case of birch cultivation, under favorable circumstances, after 10 years, the production can be tried to be sold as paper wood. Those tree species that are classified as faster rotation plantations can be converted into firewood during production. In the case of willow, higher value-added alternatives after 5 years of cultivation have not been identified due to the lack of high value-added processing alternatives

Table 3

Projected revenue from the sale of wood for biofuel (after 10 years)

Tree species	Total gain m ³ /ha	Wood price EUR/ m ³	Revenue generated, EUR
Birch	45	50*	2250
Alder	41	39**	1599
Aspen	39		1521
Willow	23	-	-
Ash	43	55*	2365

* The price of wood is determined by the prevailing market price of pulpwood

** The price of wood is determined by the prevailing market price of firewood

Source: based on Abalikštienė, Kuliešis, Tebėra, 2023; Baltpool, 2025b

The results presented in Table 3 must be interpreted responsibly. In order to grow a paper tree, at least 5 additional years of cultivation are often required, but this creates certain risks. First, the tree, as it grows longer, may begin to reach the land reclamation systems, thus damaging them. Second, the tree crown grows even more, thus obscuring the crops growing in the gaps (cereals or grass). Third, the receipt of income from agroforestry activities is postponed. However, today in Lithuania, wood panel factories, as well as clustered structures, are focused on processing wood of the lowest possible quality. By encouraging agroforestry activities, it is likely that from 2030. all wood panel factories that will exist in Lithuania at that time will be able to use 10-year-old medium and high-quality wood.

In agroforestry activities, the cultivation of melliferous plants is combined with traditional agriculture. When allocating land for agroforestry activities, the area allocated for agricultural land inevitably decreases. Table 4 assesses the financial consequences of such a decrease. Since the greatest positive environmental impact would be created in crop areas, the dynamics of the main crop crops are assessed. In this case, the income from the same hypothetical 5 ha. land area is assessed, of which 1 ha is occupied by agroforestry elements and 4 ha - by agricultural land. At the same time, a 5 percent sensitivity analysis interval is added, since the price of grain crops tends to change annually depending on global market conditions.

Table 4

Projected annual income from crop products in the agro-forestry area

Crop*	Annual income from crop production, EUR**	Total direct payments from state, EUR/ha	Total, EUR	+10 percent EUR	-10 percent EUR	Median income from agroforestry (after 10 years), EUR
Wheat	1200	110	1310	1441	1179	1000
Rapeseed	1500	110	1610	1771	1449	
Beens	900	150	1150	1265	1035	

* Wheat yield – 7 t/ha, Rapeseed yield – 4 t/ha, Bean yield – 3.5 t/ha

** Production prices – 3-month average of MATIF exchange prices

Source: based on NMA, 2025; MATIF, 2025

In the case of a small farm, it is necessary to assess the losses that are incurred when switching to agro-forestry activities. Since agro-forestry activities are currently not subsidized, the losses consist of unearned income from the main activity and unearned direct payments. The overall dynamics of income and losses is presented in Table 5. In this case, it is seen that it is necessary to create equalization mechanisms in order to achieve the scale of agroforestry required by the state. This would allow for more active implementation of environmental initiatives, while contributing to the growth of the decarbonization level of farms. The indicators presented in the table are preliminary, adapted to a farm with an average productivity score.

Table 5

Dynamics of income and losses from 1 ha of agroforestry area over 10 years

Tree type	Revenue from fuel sales, EUR	Revenue from wood sales for processing, EUR	Losses due to missed harvest, EUR	EUR Losses due to missed direct payments, EUR	Losses from organic farming payments, EUR
Birch	900	2250	12000	1200	3000
Alder	725	1599			
Aspen	525	1521			
Willow	650	-			
Ash	1000	2365			

Source: based on NMA, 2025; MATIF, 2025; Baltpool, 2025a

It is important to mention that if a farm were to start applying agroforestry initiatives independently at this time, the financial losses would consist not only of lost harvest income, but also of lost direct payments for the relevant area. In this case, no form of annual support focused on sustainability, extensive farming and the application of environmental initiatives would be available. In the short term, this will complicate the implementation and progress of agroforestry activities in the country. In the case of an organic farm, a compensation mechanism operates, allowing farms to maintain economic viability with lower harvest rates. Today, such a farm, wishing to engage in agroforestry activities, would face financial losses from the conversion of activities that would not be compensated at the state level. Another group is farms operating on highly productive lands. In individual cases, it is likely that their losses over a decade would be twice as high as in the case of an average farm. In order to encourage such farms to engage in agroforestry initiatives, it is necessary to regulate two essential aspects:

- Make changes to the legislation regarding the maximum period for growing forest plantations on agricultural land.
- Create incentive/compensation mechanisms for the application of agroforestry initiatives on agricultural land.

The calculations do not assess the payback potential. Such a decision was made due to the nuances of the current agricultural policy - a certain area on farms must still be left for non-productive activities. However, the lack of compensation for established agroforestry areas will limit the attractiveness of such activities in the future. It is likely that without direct

payments, only farms with even more arable land areas than in the calculations presented in this case will be able to engage in such activities. The main reason for such activities is risk diversification. Income from grain farming activities is unstable, and changing weather conditions can sometimes destroy the harvest. By carrying out agroforestry activities, it is possible to ensure a stable income stream, and by optimizing preparation activities, the profit obtained can exceed the profit from crop production by at least several times (depending on the type of tree). The application of the principles of economies of scale would ensure optimal economic viability for crop farms. In the case of livestock farms, income must be assessed individually. Ensuring agroforestry income streams in such farms would allow diversifying operational risks.

The calculations performed set a specific conclusion that this activity is more acceptable for landowners who do not seek to engage in daily agricultural activities. Such a model is optimal in the case when wood production is grown, and perennial grasses are grown in the interrows. This does not require significant annual investments, since the main group of annual expenses is related to the shredding of grass in the interrows. Such an activity policy would allow the state to achieve environmental goals, while somewhat slowing down the rate of loss of perennial grass areas. This would inevitably reduce the level of agricultural production, especially in regions where land areas are relatively less fertile. Land areas left for wood to grow for a longer period could lock more carbon in the soil, in turn multiplying the positive impact created on the environment. In this case, the right to make a fundamental decision falls to state institutions - despite the obvious decrease in added value per hectare and rising competition with forests, agroforestry initiatives would contribute to the decarbonization of the agricultural sector, the rational use of areas less suitable for crop production, while creating conditions for small farms to diversify the risks arising from their activities.

Conclusions

The determination of agroforestry parameters is limited by the need to select the optimal method of such farming. According to the assessment of the group of scientists, it is necessary to choose a more conservative method, allocating 20 percent of agricultural land to agroforestry. This would allow not to drastically reduce agricultural production, while ensuring environmental interests are acceptable to the state. To create a permanent income stream in the 11th year of operation, the optimal size of agroforestry areas is 20 ha. per 100 ha of farm area. In other cases, agroforestry should be treated as an opportunity to generate one-time income from the income aspect.

In the case of agroforestry, the benefits created for the state are manifested through a reduction in the intensity of agricultural land by implementing environmental protection measures. Agroforestry practice would allow achieving these goals if the area ratio were determined considering the environmental and economic balance. The main obstacle to this goal is the need for economies of scale and the lack of compensation mechanisms in the short term. This will hinder the development of agroforestry, especially in the case of small farms.

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